

Activated Charcoal: An Adsorbent with A Difference for Waste Water Purification – An Overview

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17913192>

Abstract

Activated charcoal, an unnoticed porous material but unique and powerful, has been in use for centuries in addressing the menace of wastewater, characterized by odour and colour. This paper gives an overview of its potential (activated carbon/charcoal) as an adsorbent with a difference. Its preparation and properties were also highlighted in this overview. The unique pore size/ surface area per gram (500 - 1,500 m²/g) and the catenation properties of activated carbon contributed effectively to its adsorption process for efficient removal or uptake of a broad spectrum of toxic materials from gas and liquid phases than any other material available for physical adsorption. Practical applications in its absorption capacities to textile dye-liquor (water) purification, oil spillage and medicine for the removal of contaminants or toxins in waste water and patient as gastrointestinal decontaminant were discussed. and the potential to utilize its adsorption capacities in environmental remediation of sewage water recommended. Adsorption with activated charcoal, irrespective of the sources coal or agro-wastes (agricultural waste) is an excellent way to treat solid waste effluent, offering significant benefits such as affordability, profitability, ease of operation, and efficiency in providing a greener environment.

Keywords: Activated charcoal, carbon, waste, wastewater, adsorption, absorption

1.0. Introduction

Waste is defined, according to the Webster/Oxford Dictionary, as “unwanted or unusable materials.” It is also any substance discarded after primary use that is worthless, defective, and of no use. It could be a by-product of relatively minor economic value. Table 1 depicts the United States Environmental Protection Authority [US-EPA] (2022) categorization of different types of waste. Many industrial sectors, such as the textile, paper, paint, pharmaceutical, food, leather, cosmetics, tannery, printing, and plastics industries, generated a lot of wastewaters involving dye utilizations on their products (Wong *et al.*, 2013). The wastewaters from these sources are highly toxic and have profound negative effects on aquatic life because of the waste constituents, such as nitrates, acetic acid, surfactants, enzymes chromium compounds and metals -Cu, As, Pb, Hg, Co and many auxiliary chemicals resulting from the production reactions of those goods (Kant, 2012).

In the conservation of nature for the sustenance of green environment, wastewaters are treated and among the various methods deployed are: chemical precipitation, ion exchange, coagulation and flocculation, adsorption, and membrane processes (Shafiq *et al.*, 2018; Goher *et al.*, 2015). The selection method to be used in the treatment system usually depends on the wastewater characteristics. Each treatment has its own constraints, not only in terms of cost but also in relation to feasibility, efficiency, practicability, reliability, environmental impact, sludge production, operation difficulty, pre-treatment requirements and the formation of chemical residues (Crini & Lichtfouse, 2019; Banerjee, 2020). Adsorption is one of the most effective processes of advanced wastewater treatment, which industries employ to reduce hazardous pollutants present in the effluents. This is a well-known and superior technique to other processes for removal of dyes from aqueous solution worldwide due to initial cost, operating conditions and simplicity of design (Fungaro & Magdalena, 2012). Most of commercial dye removal systems for industrial wastewater make use of activated carbon as an adsorbent (Hammed *et al.*, 2009) and also as sorbent substance in a sorption

(absorption) of petroleum products polluters of air and water by enhancing deep cleaning from oil products, without the use of chemicals to the aquatic environment. This paper share more of an overview of the uniqueness of activated carbon as its relevant to wastewater treatment, characteristics and other useful life applications.

Table 1: Waste Categorizations

Based on Matter	Degrading feature	Environmental impact	Source
Solid	Bio-degradable	Hazardous	Household
Liquid	Non-Bio-degradable	Non-hazardous	Industrial
Air emissions			Radioactive
			Electronic
			Medical
			Nuclear

(Source: US-EPA, 2022)

2.0 Water waste

Domestic wastewater, also known as municipal wastewater, is basically wastewater from residences (homes), business buildings such as hotels, and institutions (e.g., universities). Metcalf *et al.* (2013) defined wastewater as “water whose physical, chemical, or biological properties have been changed as a result of the introduction of certain substances that render it unsafe for some purposes, such as drinking.”

Man’s daily activities are majorly water - dependent and therefore discharge ‘waste’ into water. Some of these substances include body wastes (feces and urine), hair shampoo, hair, food scraps, fat, laundry powder, and the like. Invariably, much of the water supplied ends up as wastewater, which has an impact on people’s health and the environment. In the nineteenth century, flush toilets led to an increase in the volume of waste for these agricultural lands. The discharge of waste into

watercourses led to gross pollution (destruction of biodiversity and aquatic ecosystems) and health problems for downstream users. Numerous diseases are caused by contact with or consumption of contaminated water. Recently, Nigeria experienced multiple cholera outbreaks, with significant cases reported from various states, including Lagos, around June-August 2024 (Punch, 2024). It was reported in the media then that it was due to the consumption of a contaminated local drink, KUNU/SOBO, in Lagos State. Clean water is a key factor for the economic growth of any society, and this makes water treatment or purification very important. Figure 1 shows the categorization of wastewater, majorly as greywater and blackwater. Today there have been great advances to make potable water from wastewater (Amoatey & Bani 2016). In recent times, regardless of the capacity of the receiving stream, a minimum treatment level is required before discharge permits are granted by the Environmental Protection Authority of the country (Amoatey & Bani 2016; Adu-Ahyia & Anku, 2010). There are various ways of treating these wastewaters in either a central system or in a sustainable decentralized plant, and such selections usually depend on the wastewater characteristics and the chemical composition of the waste (Shafiq *et al.*, 2018; Goher *et al.*, 2015). Other factors considered are feasibility, efficiency, practicability, reliability, environmental impact, sludge production, operation difficulty, and pre-treatment requirements. (Crini & Lichtfouse, 2019). All treatments focus on the reduction of biodegradable organic substances, nutrient concentration, and elimination of pathogens in the waste for a clean environment.

3.0 Adsorption and Absorption

These two technical terms sound almost similar, but there is much difference between absorption and adsorption. The main difference between them is that adsorption is defined by Gabelman (2019) as “a unit operation that exploits the adhesion or attraction of solutes—atoms, molecules, or ions—from a gas, liquid, or dissolved solid in a liquid to a solid surface.” This process creates a film of the adsorbate (usually solute) on the surface of the adsorbent, which is the solid. The process is a surface phenomenon (like the settlement of dust particles on the surfaces of a table). The adsorbate does not penetrate through the material surface and into the bulk of the adsorbent. This process (adsorption) differs from absorption, in which a fluid (the absorbate) is dissolved by or permeates a liquid or solid (the absorbent). It is a bulk phenomenon—similar to dyeing of fabric (Figure 2)—and adsorption often precedes absorption. There is another technical word called sorption, which encompasses both adsorption and absorption, which is usually effective in many unit operations, such as in dyeing fabrics. Desorption is the reverse of sorption. It is a physical process where adsorbed atoms or molecules are released from the surface into the surrounding vacuum or fluid. This occurs when a molecule gains enough energy to overcome the activation barrier and the binding energy that keeps it attached to the surface (Negm *et al.*, 2017; Abesekara *et al.*, 2020). Among all the various treatments available for wastewater purification, adsorption using activated carbon is very popular. Though the high cost of the raw material (coal-based activated carbon) is the major challenge (Research & Market, 2018), this has necessitated researchers to adjust the adsorption method by substituting the utilization of commercial adsorbent for agricultural waste (Alalwan *et al.*, 2020; Yunus *et al.*, 2019; Saxena *et al.*, 2017; Negm *et al.*, 2017).

In the treatment process (adsorption), adsorption requires surface energy, just like surface tension. Bonding (or force of attachment—ionic, covalent, or metallic) is involved, and the exact nature of the bonding depends on the details of the species of the adsorbate and adsorbent involved. Generally, the adsorption process, which is determined during the isotherm and kinetic study, is classified as physisorption (a characteristic of weak van der Waals forces) or chemisorption

(characteristic of covalent bonding) (Abesekara *et al.*, 2020; Ayob *et al.*, 2021). It may also occur due to electrostatic attraction. The nature of the adsorption can affect the structure of the adsorbed species, and full details of the determinations of these kinetics and thermokinetics of the interactions are found in the literature (Sims *et al.*, 2019; Milan, 2014; Mathew *et al.*, 2016; Kwon *et al.*, 2011).

Figure 2: Graphic Representations of Adsorption and Absorption

4.0 Adsorbents

Adsorbents are substances that trap or adsorb another substance. They are usually in the form of spherical pellets, rods, moldings, or monoliths with a hydrodynamic radius between 0.25 and 5 mm. They have high abrasion resistance, high thermal stability, and small pore diameters—for a higher exposed surface area and high capacity for adsorption (Gabelman, 2019). The industrial adsorbents currently and previously used are:

- Oxygen-containing compounds are typically hydrophilic and polar, including materials such as silica gel, limestone (calcium carbonate), and zeolites.

- Carbon-based compounds are typically hydrophobic (water-resistant) and non-polar, including materials such as activated carbon and graphite.
- Polymer-based compounds are polar or non-polar, depending on the functional groups in the polymer matrix.
- Agro-industrial waste materials, granular or powdered activated carbon (AC), and modified AC (Shahrakia *et al.*, 2021). Activated carbon (AC) is a popular adsorbent due to its high adsorption capacity owing to its porous structure and surface chemical groups. Its high surface area is due to the development of mainly microporous and mesoporous materials of different sizes and shapes. The presence of different pore size distributions influences the performance properties of the AC. Macro-pores have little contribution to the development of surface area.

5.0 Activated Carbon / Charcoal

Activated carbon (also known as activated charcoal) is a highly porous, amorphous solid consisting of microcrystallites with a graphite lattice, usually prepared in small pellets or a powder. It is nonpolar and cheap and reacts with oxygen at moderate temperatures (over 300 °C). It is a highly effective and versatile adsorbent widely used in various applications, from water purification to air filtration and medical treatments (David, 2016). The uniqueness in the property of activated carbon or charcoal is due to the unique attributes of carbon atoms that form the major composition of the material. Carbon has a capacity of being able to bond together to form very long, durable chains with or without branches or rings of various sizes and often contains thousands of carbon atoms, called catenation (Figure 3).

Chain

Ring

Branched chain

Figure 3: The Power of Carbon – Catenation

Again, carbon is the only chemical element that has a major field of chemistry devoted to the study of its compounds, called organic chemistry. Over 95% of millions of chemical compounds are carbon compounds, and most organic compounds come from living things or things that were once living, such as crude oil and coal. Life chemistry is carbon chemistry, and what makes carbon suitable for life also makes it suitable for many industrial processes. All these set activated carbon/charcoal apart from other adsorbents. Table 2 shows the chemical and physical parameters of activated charcoal that significantly influence its performance as an adsorbent over others in adsorbing various contaminants. A teaspoon of activated carbon has more surface area (500 - 1,500 m²/g) than a football field (4,050 - 10,800 m²) (Nowicki, 2016). Several factors can influence its adsorptive capacity, such as temperature, pore size, particle size, surface area, solubility and toxic ionization stage, the pH, the presence of inorganic salts, and the gastric contents (Bonilla-Velez & Marin-Cuero, 2017).

Table 2: The Chemical and Physical Parameters of Activated Charcoal

Parameters	Qualities
Chemical Composition	-majorly carbon (usually >85-90%), - coconut shells, fruits wood
Surface area	-high surface area, Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) 500 - 1,500 m ² /g.
Porous structure / Pore Size	-highly porous structure <2nm ->50nm Ø
Chemical Reactivity	-Highly modifiable for functional group addition
pH range & Density	-pH:6-10; 0.2-0.5g/cm ³
Moisture & Thermal stability	-M.C: < below 5% ; stable up to 600 -1,000°C
Regenerability	-easily reuseable - thermal regeneration method
Biocompatibility	-Highly biocompatible & non-toxic for medical use
Applications	-highly versatile (-across various industries)
Cost-Effectiveness	- relatively cost-effective, widely available & ease of preparation

6.0. Activated Carbon Preparation Method

Activated carbon is a mixture of particles that are insoluble and are manufactured from numerous/diverse carbonaceous materials, including coal (bituminous, subbituminous, and lignite), peat, wood, or nutshells (e.g., coconut). Research has shown that coconut shell (CS) and coal give ideal adsorption efficiency, and they are commonly used in industrial manufacturing to make commercial AC (Ayob *et al.*, 2021). The manufacturing process consists of two phases: carbonization and activation (Figure 4). The carbonization process includes drying and then heating to separate by-products, including tars and other hydrocarbons, from the raw material, as well as to drive off any gases generated. The process is completed by heating the material over 400 °C (750 °F) in an oxygen-free atmosphere that cannot support combustion (Mohammad-Khah & Ansari, 2009).

Figure 4: Flow chart of preparation of Activated Charcoal (Source: Sunmit-Dhawane, 2024)

Thereafter, the carbonized particles are "activated" by subjecting them to a high temperature (800-1000°C) oxidant, usually steam or carbon dioxide, and the incomplete combustion products burn up and volatilize, eroding the internal surfaces of the product. This action tremendously increases the adsorptive surface area of the carbon (Figure 5) (Fungaro & Magdalena, 2012; Metcalf *et al.*, 2013). The amount of time they spend in this stage determines the size of the pores that form during the activation phase. Pore diameters increase with longer exposure periods (Mohammad-Khah & Ansari, 2009). Fungaro & Magdalena (2012) reported that the average surface area for activated charcoal is 800-1,200 m²/g. "Superactivated" charcoal may have a surface area of 2,800-3,500 m²/g and can adsorb greater quantities of the substance. This high surface area of the carbon arises from the development of microporous and mesoporous materials of different sizes and shapes, which influences the performance properties of the AC.

Nowicki (2016) reported that activated carbon does not last forever in that the pores or physical adsorption spaces, which are nanometer-sized volumes between the graphitic platelets, are eventually filled and are no longer capable of removing adsorbates (solutes). Hence, a periodic change-out with fresh virgin or reactivated carbon is desired. Carbon pores are heterogeneous and vary in adsorption energy from strong to weak.

Figure 5: Gradual activation process of carbon during thermal treatment (Source: Mohammad-Khah & Ansari, 2009)

7.0. Applications and economic benefits of activated carbon

Researches are showing that activated charcoal is a versatile adsorbent used on a diverse adsorbate in an aqueous environment to mitigate water pollution that causes environmental problems (Omokpariola & Otuosorochi, 2020; Ayob *et al.*, 2021). Nearly all industrial sectors generate one

toxic chemical or another in different concentrations in their wastewater during the course of their productions. The utilization of agro-materials for the production of activated charcoal for adsorption studies had recorded a tremendous success (in terms of its particle pore sizes, surface areas, and other parameters) comparable to the commercial activated charcoal, which is costly. Adetuyi *et al.* (2009) and Adetuyi & Jabar (2011) did a comparative study of applying activated carbon from five biosolid agricultural wastes and that of commercial activated charcoal in an adsorption study of removing dye (indigo) from dyeing effluent (wastewater). Table 3 shows the result of the findings confirming the potency of the activated carbons deployed; both the commercial and the agro-agricultural waste performed satisfactorily in dye removal. Activated carbon has a broad spectrum of adsorption of organic substances and non-polar adsorbates of various industrial wastewaters and is useful as a sorbent substance in the sorption of petroleum pollutants of oil on water (Esfahlan *et al.*, 2020; Sabadash & Lysko, 2023). Poisonings impact the patient's health through either local or systemic effects, which are caused by the ingestion of different toxic substances (acids, bases, salts, heavy metals, and numerous chemicals that are found in some household products) (Bonilla-Velez & Marin-Cuero, 2017). Medically, activated charcoal is used for a variety of health-related applications—to reduce excessive gas in the digestive tract (Alina, 2023; David, 2016; Olson, 2010) and prevention of adsorption of poisons/toxins in the body (gastrointestinal decontamination). Charcoal, as gastrointestinal decontamination, is the most commonly used in the initial management of patients' administration as soon as possible for maximum action with acute intoxications (Mowry *et al.*, 2015; Bonilla-Velez & Marin-Cuero, 2017). It adsorbs substances localized in the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) and retains them within the charcoal, thus minimizing the absorption through the mucosa in the GIT into the bloodstream and reducing or preventing systemic toxicity (Jurgens *et al.*, 2009; Bonilla-Velez & Marin-Cuero, 2017). Research has shown that the efficacy of AC reduces with time from the point of ingestion to AC administration and also with the presence of food in the GIT, among other factors. Other uses include dehumidification and air purification in bathrooms (David, 2016) and also for washing teeth (Adetuyi, 2024). Activated carbon can act as a filter material in air cleaning filters

for removal of gases and vapors in the industrial environment, and impregnated grades of it (activated charcoal) are used as cigarette filters to adsorb some of the harmful components of tobacco. Activated charcoal is a very good detoxifier (David, 2016). A lot of its usefulness and mechanism of actions as a unit process are found in the literature (Mohammad-Khah & Ansari, 2009; Bonilla-Velez & Marin-Cuero, 2017). Economically, it can serve as a source of income for individuals and corporate bodies and as foreign exchange for the country.

Table 3: Effect of adsorbent dosage in Indigo removal from its effluent

Adsorbent Dosage(g)	ACBC %removal	AAC %removal	AWLC %removal	AEGC %removal	ACS %removal	PAC %removal
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.20	86.17	79.28	81.23	74.23	56.60	86.60
0.40	92.83	87.23	89.36	82.34	69.57	94.46
0.60	95.96	91.91	94.68	91.49	73.40	96.34
0.80	97.23	95.74	95.11	95.53	76.38	97.20
1.00	97.66	96.82	96.88	96.80	82.34	97.87

Key: **ACBC** -Activated cattle bone carbon; **AAC**- Activated algae carbon,
AWLC- Activated water lettuce carbon; **AEGC**- Activated elephant grass carbon,
ACS - Activated crab shell and **PAC- powder activated carbon**
(Source: Adetuyi, and Jabar, (2011); Adetuyi, 2019)

8.0 Utilization of Treated Wastewater

The large volume of water supplies that ends up as wastewater daily in municipal sectors could be treated and recycled for productive usage (Koboević & Kurtela, 2011; Kirmizi, 2019). This will

mitigate against the health challenges of the citizenry and salvage our biodiversity and aquatic ecosystems. The wastewater, particularly the grey categories from domestic sources, could be channeled, after treatment in either a central or decentralized plant with activated charcoal (adsorbent), into our agricultural sector for irrigation of crops, grasses, trees, and horticulture flowers around homes, schools, and farmlands in the country. Irrigated water pipes are seen everywhere around their plants and crops. Most countries, particularly Israel and Egypt, have adopted this method to boost their agricultural productions.

9.0. Conclusion

Activated carbon/charcoal (AC), regardless of its sources, is a very potent adsorbent that will continue to be in use in the adsorption unit operation process for efficient removal or uptake of a broad spectrum of toxic materials from gas and liquid phases of aqueous media. Its health usage is numerous and unquantifiable in providing an immediate remediation/relief for intoxicant patients suffering from ingestion of harmful/poisonous substances, overdose, or venom from stinging insects and snakes. Adsorption with activated charcoal is an excellent way to treat solid waste effluent, offering significant benefits such as affordability, profitability, ease of operation, and efficiency in providing a greener environment. Activated carbon/charcoal (AC) is eco-friendly in nature.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author would like to acknowledge the management of Trinity University City Campus, Sabo, Yaba, Lagos, and the faculty members of Basic Medical and Applied Sciences (FBMAS) for the support received to deliver the faculty lecture in November 2024 on charcoal and the preparation of this manuscript.

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